

1 **4-1bb loss is associated with IL-23 deficiency.**

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7 We recently described the set of component genes in the exhaustion and senescence gene expression
8 programs, and described the function of CD137 in these immune and cellular arousal state programs.
9 We recently demonstrated that the cell surface receptor CD137, also known as 4-1bb, is a primary target
10 of the NOD2 transcriptional program, an exhaustion receptor with immune functions whose expression is
11 lost in cells expressing an IBD-associated NOD2 mutation. We demonstrate here that 4-1bb expression in
12 certain cell types of the hematopoietic system in humans is specifically associated with expression of the
13 major IBD protective factor, *IL23*. Low expression of 4-1bb in immune cells sorted based on 4-1bb
14 expression (4-1bb(lo) and 4-1bb(hi)) confirmed that absence or loss of 4-1bb is specifically associated with
15 deficiency of the IL-23 cytokine and receptor. Transgenic 4-1bb receptor expression in regulatory T-cells
16 results in activation of the IL-23 cytokine subunit IL-23a and the receptor for the IL-23 cytokine, IL-23R.
17 4-1bb loss is associated with IL-23 deficiency. We demonstrate here a novel mechanism by which an IBD
18 susceptibility allele results in context-specific IL-23 deficiency.
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